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A Public Key Infrastructure for Smart Charging

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Summary

With charging stations getting smarter and smarter, the data flow becoming more extensive and complex, it becomes necessary to properly arrange data security. It is of great importance to embed security in the new energy system before the large uptake of electric mobility will take place.

Keywords: safety, interoperability, market, EV, smart charging

1 Scale up

With the rise of electric cars and the charging of them, safe and cyber secure charging will be a crucial part of the electricity system in the near future. With new techniques and protocols, *such* as ISO 15118 and OCPP, communication between the vehicle and the grid heavily relies on measurements and data. The integrity and authenticity of data must be of uncontested reliability. Together with the need for better cyber security on devices, the need for better security of the infrastructure grows together with the consumers wish for choices and a seamless service.

In September 2019, ElaadNL organized a roundtable conference on this topic [1]. In the Netherlands we have the fortunate situation that since 2011 all EV drivers are able to charge anywhere they like. This freedom of interoperability is now spreading across Europe, but the market is still very fragmented.

2 Cyber security on devices

To make charging infrastructure secure we should at least address these five issues. To start, a future-proof design should be created with enough computational power and memory resources. These resources are needed to be able to handle future algorithms, protocols, and firmware updates. Second, the cryptographic algorithms and protocols of today are well known and considered secure. However, it could be that a vulnerability is found which requires to switch to a different algorithm. The requirement to follow the latest security advices and apply cryptographic agility should be part of the requirements or regulation regarding roll out of charging infrastructure. Third, communication to and from the device(s) should be secured by encryption and digital signatures, for example by Transport Layer Security (TLS). The fourth topic is creating norms and standards regarding resilience and system hardening. Charging stations should have unused interfaces disabled, and maintenance interfaces secured. The charging station should not crash or show any other unintended behavior when malicious messages are sent; the infrastructure should be able to detect a different format and handle it accordingly. Since the ability to charge is part of the vital infrastructure, the last topic regards the physical testing of the cyber security of devices in a certified laboratory.

3 Cyber security on the public key infrastructure

Apart from the need for better cyber security on devices, consumers have a wish for choices and a seamless service. If within the automotive and energy, sectors are unable to agree on a common technology and implementation, resulting in losing interoperability. Losing interoperability is bad for both innovation in the sector and consumers. An agreement between players in the market is not yet in sight.

4. Open design

How can we align market players and still have better cyber security on the infrastructure? This can be achieved with a public key infrastructure (PKI) with an open design[2]. Multiple designs for setting up a PKI using ISO 15118 are possible. Models vary from a system managed by a single party or a consortium of parties, to an open PKI that allows everybody in the EV market to participate [3]. ElaadNL identified five options for a PKI: 1) a PKI consortium; 2) multiple PKIs; 3) a certificate trust list based PKI; 4) walking chain of trust; 5) a European authority PKI.

Fig. 1 different technical options have different levels of market acceptance

A poll organized by ElaadNL on the round table event of September 2019 showed the OEMs and representatives from the research sector are in favour of multiple PKIs or a Certificate Trust List based PKI. Legislative experts and policy makers chose the European authority PKI. The same goes for the representatives from the e-mobility sector. Furthermore, the votes of charging operators were distributed among all the five options. We thus see clear differences in preference between the different sectors involved in e-mobility.

4.1. One PKI consortium

In an ideal world only one PKI is needed and possible for EV charging. Governance, technologic improvements and operations could be done by experts. This is the most basic option; to let all parties reside under one root Certificate Authority (CA). All market parties share their trust and their business into this Authority. Their customer experience, their cost model, technical solutions, B2B contracts etc. Because this root CA and this PKI is in fact a monopoly there should be clear, transparent, supported rules and a neutral and independent regulator.

However, the PKI for (smart) charging is a global operation. Different countries on different continents have a different pace of roll out of electric mobility. Visions on governance might vary between countries, or within a sector. The PKI shall be a cross sector operation, with players in automotive, energy and possibly banking and internet. Therefore, in our opinion, it must be clear that the root authority should themselves not be a player in the EV or automotive sector, because the authority cannot be an ally to a specific group of market participants. The world of EV is currently a too much fragmented platform for the top-down hierarchy needed for a one PKI consortium.

4.2. Multiple PKI's

There can also be a single body that overlooks the ecosystem, but ownership is distributed among many players, resulting in a federal scheme. In this scheme, market parties will join as many PKIs as possible. Original equipment manufacturers (OEM) adopt multiple root certificates into their EVs. Charge Point Operators (CPO) will also adopt multiple root certificates into their charging stations. These solution may not be scalable, since there are limitations on the number of root certificates to be adopted. At a certain stage, multiple PKIs exist independently next to each other, not trusting each other.

4.3. Certificate trustlist based PKI

When several PKIs coexist, each with their own certification chain, the PKIs can express their trust in each other. An administrative authority might evolve with a mission to create a unique trust list. The authority keeps the list updated and distributes it to all relevant parties. Charging stations and EVs must be equipped to handle this trust list as a source of trusted root CA's.

To enable the transition towards multiple PKI's and their CA there can be worries about the scalability of the system. It might be impossible to be able to predict with any sort of inclusiveness what the right root CA's are that need to be installed in the cars. Furthermore, the ISO 15118 standard requires at least one root certificate for the EV, but the note related to it recommends a minimum of 5 certificates. The charging station shall support the storage of at least 10 V2G root Certificates. Given these ISO 15118 specifications, OEM's might limit the number of CA's in the EV, thus frustrating interoperability and the scale up of the system.

4.4. Walking chain of trust

Large players may require multiple CAs in various geographic regions. Cross-certification allows different CAs to deploy and maintain trusted relationships. For cross-certification two operations have to be undertaken. First, a trusted relationship between two CAs has to be established. In the case of bilateral cross-certification, two CAs securely exchange their verification keys. These are the keys used to verify the CAs' signatures on certificates. To complete the operation, each CA signs the other CA's verification key in a certificate referred to as a "cross-certificate". Second, on the client-side software, the trustworthiness of a user certificate signed by a cross-certified CA should be verified. The operation is often referred to as "walking a chain of trust". The "chain" refers to a list of cross-certificate validations that are "walked" (or traced) from the CA key of the verifying user to the CA key required to validate the other user's certificate. When walking a chain of cross-certificates, each cross-certificate must be checked to ensure that it is still trusted. User certificates must be able to be revoked; so must cross-certificates. This requirement is frequently overlooked in discussions regarding cross-certification [4].

A bridge PKI is a number of PKIs that each cross-sign each other. It is a collaborative approach of multiple PKI's cross signed. Bridge PKI's are already used in different sectors, such as the internet. Key requirement is that the EV PKI is highly responsive, as responsive as the web PKI. This is because the lifetime of the EV is long; a vehicle of today might still be there in twenty years' time. Therefore, it must be able to adapt to the technology of tomorrow.

4.5. European authority.

The question is not whether the limitation of five PKIs are sufficient to serve the market. The question is what our starting point is to develop a transparent, trusted, safe, simple, fast, cost-efficient and legal PKI that supports the level playing field in e-mobility. To avoid scalability problems, or too long, uncontrollable chains of trust. There is a need for an open standard and a level playing field between different regions and sectors. A neutral and independent referee in case of disputes. Therefore there is a role for an European Authority to oversee the governance of the PKI.

4.6. A timeline

From one PKI, the architecture is evolving to multiple PKIs. This allows competition and competition will reduce costs. However, at the stage of development of multiple PKIs interoperability is lost. Technical standards on quality and cyber security are needed before the architecture can grow to a next stage, where marketplaces start to trust each other. Once marketplaces trust each other, a certificate trust list, cross-signing can take place or a bridge PKI

most CPOs have much less negotiating power. Furthermore, the Electro Mobility Service Providers (EMSP) are fully dependent on the OEMs' cooperation.

Unlike today, the OEM will need to agree to the EMSP that a consumer selects (by providing the OEM provisioning certificate). OEMs are themselves in competition with these EMSPs, since all OEMs are setting up EMSP services themselves (moving up the value chain). This technicality means that non-OEM EMSPs are at a great disadvantage, a market imbalance that can only be addressed by market rules and governance.

5.2 Fair and reasonable

OEMs are investing in their own Charging Infrastructure (moving up the value chain), giving discounts and privileges to consumers that drive their vehicle brand by means of favoring a certain EMSP that is owned or preferred by the OEM (for example cheap Plug&Charge service from this EMSP combined with uncompetitive pricing for direct payments or roaming conditions for other EMSPs). Consumers that want to charge with a competing vehicle brand should have access under fair and reasonable conditions, particularly when the infrastructure is in the public space and concessions are involved. What is fair and reasonable can be neutrally agreed in market rules and governance.

All in all, the market will enter a very competitive phase, where market players will venture up and down the value chain and where the size of a company matters when it comes to negotiations. A market dictated by large companies or companies that operate directly or indirectly – without clear rules – in multiple market roles will very likely not provide the needed innovation, service and price pressure. Ultimately, most probably the OEMs and possible also large CPOs, Utility Companies and Energy Companies may become too dominant in the development of the e-mobility market which will in turn lead to a slower transition of the mobility sector.

6. Market rules

A good thing is that general legislation regarding consumer protection and industry competition already is in place in Europe and many other countries. In the emerging field of e-mobility this could first be translated to consumer freedom to select and change the EMSP at any time, regardless of the brand, origin or original destination of the vehicle. Second, consumer freedom to charge at any charging station, regardless of the vehicle brand or the E-mobility Service Provider can be based on existing consumer protection. Measures by the European Parliament concerning open internet access could apply for charging; *"Providers of internet access services shall treat all traffic equally, when providing internet access services, without discrimination, restriction or interference, and irrespective of the sender and receiver, the content accessed or distributed, the applications or services used or provided, or the terminal equipment used"*[8]. Third, consumers should be informed upfront about the tariff of charging at any charge station. This is the tariff the E-mobility Service Provider will bill towards the EV driver. All tariffs shown towards the consumer must be understandable and without hidden cost. Last, market access under fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory conditions for all market parties should also apply.

For the specific design of a PKI, it should in our opinion be drawn along some indicators which should:

- 1 be trusted by all market parties,
- 2 be simple, can be set up quickly, fast in implementation of upgrades,
- 3 cost not too much to set up and maintain,
- 4 respect all the legal requirements and creates a level playing field
- 5 have clear, non-discriminatory rules for participation and a neutral authority to guard these 5 indicators

7. European embedment

The revision of the Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Directive might be the proper platform to formalize these market rules and embed them in legislation [9]. To govern the set-up and compliance of market rules, an independent European Authority should be in place to monitor prices and fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory access. The European Authority should act as an intermediate in case of conflict and guarantee interoperability for consumers. It should organize the acceptance of new V2G Root CAs and SubCAs and monitor the quality level and Independent Quality Audit results. It may be the case the regulator has to create a "super root" that supercedes the 5 V2G roots.

8. Conclusions

With charging stations getting smarter and smarter, the data flow becomes more extensive and it is necessarily to properly arrange data security. It is of great importance to embed security in the new energy system before the large uptake of electric mobility will take place. The rising e-mobility market needs a transparent, trusted, safe, simple, fast, cost-efficient and legal PKI that creates a level playing field between all market actors and allows for fair competition between them.

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